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ANTIHYPERGLYCEMIC ACTIVITY OF *HOLOSTEMMA ANNULARIS* K. SCHUM ROOT EXTRACTS IN STREPTOZOTOCIN-INDUCED DIABETIC WISTAR RATS

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ABSTRACT

As incidence of diabetes is increasing worldwide, besides it is associated with complications, this study aimed to evaluate the Anti-hyperglycemic activity of the roots of *Holostemma annularis* K. Schum (Asclepiadaceae) in Streptozotocin (STZ) induced diabetic Wistar rats. Diabetes as induced in rats by an intraperitoneal injection of streptozotocin (50 mg/kg). Extract was orally administered to diabetic rats for a period of 16 days. Animals were divided into seven groups (n=6) receiving different treatments: Group I: Normal (Control), Group II: Diabetic (control), Group III: Standard drug glibenclamide (5 mg/kg, orally). Group IV and Group V: Chloroform Extract of *Holostemma annularis* (CEHA 150 and 300 mg/kg) and Group VI and Group VII Alcoholic Extract of *Holostemma annularis* (AEHA) (150 and 300 mg/kg). Blood serum was analyzed for the following biochemical parameters like serum glucose, serum insulin, Urine creatinine, total proteins in urine and histopathological study of pancreas was examined. Significant results were observed in the estimated parameters. It is concluded that, the anti-hyperglycemic effect of Chloroform and Alcoholic extracts of *Holostemma annularis* may be due to both reductions in glucose level and improvement in histopathological studies. Hence, it is proved that *Holostemma annularis* is having anti diabetic activity in streptozotocin induced diabetic rats.

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a group of metabolic disorders characterized by elevated plasma glucose levels. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 180 million people worldwide are currently living with this disorder, with these numbers looking set to double by the year 2030 [1]. It is estimated that at least 1 in 20 deaths, globally and across all ages, are attributable to diabetes [2]. About 80% of all diabetes deaths occur in the low and middle income segments, with the greatest increases expected in Africa and Asia [3, 4]. The increase in incidence of diabetes in developing countries follows the trend of urbanization and lifestyle changes, perhaps most importantly a “Western-style” diet. Together with inadequate blood sugar control, there are several other chronic and acute complications associated with diabetes. Vascular complications include retinopathy, nephropathy, neuropathy and coronary artery, cerebrovascular and peripheral vascular diseases [5]. WHO estimates that India will have 79.9 million diabetes by 2030 and a quarter of the income is devoted to diabetic care for a low income Indian family. Every fifth adult of the world is an Indian, for which India is considered as the Diabetic capital by International Diabetic Federation [6].

Type 1 diabetes (T1D) - Insulin Dependent Diabetes mellitus (IDDM) is a severe autoimmune disease, mediated by auto reactive T cells targeting a number of endogenous proteins, primarily pro insulin, glutamic acid decarboxylase, protein tyrosine phosphatase like protein and zinc transporter. At the same time, auto antibodies against islet proteins are produced by plasma cells and may contribute to the pathogenesis [7, 8]. These auto antibodies are used as main predictors of T1D risk. Genetics play a minor role in defining T1D risk, with the human leukocyte antigen (HLA) region as the only major genetic predictor [9]. In contrast, a number of environmental factors can mediate the progression to T1D. Thus, reduced load of infection, specific viral infection, dietary components, and beta cell hyperactivity have all been shown to be T1D risk factors.

Although life saving, insulin is not a curative treatment for T1D. The patients are critically dependent on administration of the hormone for the rest of their life, and in spite of careful medical attention, a significant proportion of the patients develop serious complications involving kidneys, eyes, heart and peripheral nerves. Furthermore, the development of highly purified or genetically modified insulin's has not improved the long term survival of the patients [10].

The major four categories of oral antidiabetic agents are Insulin secretagogues (sulfonylureas), Biguanides, Thiazolidinediones and Alpha glucosidase inhibitors. The primary mechanism of action of sulfonylureas is enhancement of insulin secretion. Seven sulfonylurea drugs are available and are conventionally divided in to first and second generation agents, which differ primarily in their potency.

STZ is toxic to the insulin producing beta cells of the Islets of Langerhans in the pancreas, and thus it is widely employed to induce experimental diabetes in animals. Administration of a single dose of STZ (40 mg/kg, 50 mg/kg, 55 mg/kg, 60 mg/kg and 65 mg/kg i.p. or i.v.) in rats results in hyperglycemia within 72 hours [11, 12, 13, 14, 15 & 16]. Though the development of modern medicine resulted in the advent of modern pharmaceuticals including insulin, Biguanides, sulfonylurea's and thiazolidine diones there is still a need to look for new drugs as no drug has been shown to control diabetic complications effectively. It is necessary to evaluate plant species traditionally used against diabetes mellitus to discover new compounds that can be used effectively against this disease as well as lessen diabetic complications. Interestingly, the parent compound of Biguanides used in the treatment of insulin resistance was originally isolated from a plant source French lilac [17].

Holostemma annularis is a twining shrub with large flowers. Chemical investigation of root revealed the presence α -amyrin, lupeol, β -sitosterol and 6-amino acids, Viz. alanine, aspartic acid, glycine, serine, threonine and valine [18]. The roots of *Holostemma* are useful in ophthalmopathy, orchitis, cough, burning sensation, stomachalgia, constipation, fever and tridoshas. The root is also used in spermatorrhoea and reported to possess cooling, tonic and lactative properties. Root paste is applied in ophthalmia and orchitis. It is given in diabetes with water and used along with *Bombax ceiba* to treat leucorrhoea. Flowers paste is applied externally in itching and in insect bite. Plant is used to cure ulcers, diseases of blood, gonorrhoea, cough and vesicular calculi [19, 20]. In the present study we have investigated the antidiabetic effect of Chloroform and alcohol extract of *Holostemma annularis* roots extract in streptozotocin-induced diabetes in preclinical model.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Plant Material:

The roots of *Holostemma annularis* were collected from Herbal Folk Research Centre (Reg.No.37 of 1998) Tirupathi, Andhra Pradesh (India). It was authenticated by taxonomist Prof, Vedhavathy, and a voucher specimen was deposited in S.V.University.

Extraction of Plant Material:

The *Holostemma annularis* roots were dried under room temperature, until free from the moisture. Finally, the dried roots were powdered coarsely and then passed through sieve No. 44 to get uniform powder. The coarse powder obtained was extracted with petroleum ether to remove the fatty substances; the marc was further extracted exhaustively with chloroform and Alcohol separately in a Soxhlet apparatus and filtered. The extract was concentrated under reduced temperature and pressure to get dry residue and stored in desiccators. The chloroform and alcohol extract of *Holostemma annularis* was prepared using 2% (v/v) Tween-80 daily for oral administration.

Chemicals:

Streptozotocin and glibenclamide was purchased from Sigma Chemicals Co (St. Louis, Mo, USA), Glucometer and glucometer strips obtained from (Roche Diagnostic, USA). All other chemicals used in this study were of analytical grade and obtained from SRL Chemicals, Mumbai, India.

Animals:

Forty-two adult male *Wistar* albino rats with a weight of 180-220g were used for the experiment. The rats were fed with standard laboratory chow and water before the experiment. They were divided into 7 groups (n=6) and housed in cages. The animals were acclimatized to laboratory conditions for one week before commencement of experiment. The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (NIP/1330/AC/10/CPCSEA Dated 11th March), Nizam Institute of Pharmacy, (Hyderabad, Andhra Pradesh, India) and the rats were maintained in accordance with the National Institute of Nutrition, Indian Council of Medical Research, Hyderabad, India guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals.

Induction of Experimental Diabetes [21]:

Diabetes was induced in overnight fasted rats by intra-peritoneal injection of streptozotocin (50 mg/kg, b.w.) dissolved in 0.9% ice-cold saline immediately before use. To prevent the hypo glycemia which occurred during the first 24 h following the Streptozotocin administration, 5% glucose solution was orally given to the diabetic rats. Seventy-two hours after streptozotocin administration blood samples were withdrawn by retro-orbital puncture and glucose levels determined to confirm diabetes. The diabetic rats were exhibiting blood glucose levels in the range of 180 and 280 mg/100 ml were selected for the studies. These diabetic rats were sub-divided into 7 groups of 6 rats each, were used for the study. The study was carried out for 16 days. Blood was collected by retro-orbital puncture under light ether anesthesia on the 1st, 4th, 7th, 10th, 13th and 16th day. Urine was collected on the last day of study for 24 hrs by using metabolic cage for further biochemical estimation.

Experimental Design:

Normal and diabetic rats were divided into seven groups (n=6) and were treated daily orally for 16 days. Group I: Normal control received distilled water (2ml/kg/day, p.o.). Group II: Diabetic control received distilled water (2ml/kg/day, p.o.). Group III: Diabetic rats treated with glibenclamide (5mg/kg/day, p.o.). Group IV: Diabetic rats treated with CEHA (150 mg/kg/ day, p.o.). Group V: Diabetic rats treated with CEHA (300 mg/kg/ day, p.o.). Group-VI: Diabetic rats treated with AEHA (150 mg/kg/ day, p.o.). And Group-VII diabetic rats treated with AEHA (300 mg/kg/ day, p.o.). Glucose levels were estimated using a glucose oxidase peroxidase reactive strips and a glucometer (Accu-check, Roche Diagnostics, USA). At the end of experimental period, all the rats were sacrificed by cervical decapitation. Blood samples were collected, allowed to clot. Serum was separated by centrifuging for 15 min and analyzed for various biochemical parameters. A part of pancreas was fixed in 10% formalin for histopathological studies.

Biochemical Parameters:

Blood was collected in a heparin coated tubes and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. Serum glucose level was estimated by GOD-POD method using a commercial kit (Span diagnostics, India). Urine creatinine, Urine Total Proteins was measured using Autoanalyser and serum insulin levels were estimated by ACS: 180 Automated Chemiluminescence systems at Pathcare Labs Pvt Ltd, Hyderabad.

Statistical analysis:

All values were expressed as the mean \pm (S.D.). The differences were compared using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Dunnett's test. P values < 0.05 were considered to be significant.

RESULTS:**Effect on blood glucose and plasma Insulin levels:**

Single dose intra-peritoneal treatment of rats with streptozotocin (50 mg/kg) significantly ($p < 0.001$) raised blood sugar level from 3rd day to 16th day of the study in diabetic control group. As shown in (Table-1), treatment with Glibenclamide (5 mg/kg, orally) has reduced streptozotocin increased blood glucose level significantly ($p < 0.001$). Administration of *Holostemma annularis* chloroform and alcoholic extract 150 and 300 mg/kg p.o, significantly ($p < 0.001$) attenuated streptozotocin induced increased blood glucose level from 4th to 16th day of study. As shown in (Table-2), both the extracts of *Holostemma annularis* at 150 and 300 mg/kg dose p.o. After 16 days of treatment significantly increase in serum insulin level when compared to normal and diabetic control groups

Effect on urine creatinine & total proteins levels:

Administration of both chloroform and alcoholic extract (150 and 300 mg/kg) significantly decreased ($p < 0.05$ and 0.01) renal creatinine when compared to streptozotocin induced diabetic rats. Similarly treatment with *Holostemma annularis* root extract at all doses reduced total protein significantly ($p < 0.01$) when compared to diabetic control group animals (Table-3).

Histopathological evaluation of pancreas:

The biochemical parameters were supplemented with histopathological studies of pancreas (Fig-1). The normal architecture of pancreatic tissue of pancreatic sections stained with haematoxylin and eosin demonstrated that administration of STZ caused necrotic changes of pancreatic islets. Changes like karyolysis, disappearing of nucleus and destructed cells were visible. It showed markedly dilated and congested blood vessels, vacuolar degeneration in the cells of islets of langerhans in the center. Some parts of pancreas showed flattening of the nuclei. Administration of *Holostemma annularis* and glibenclamide treated diabetic animals was milder than that found in the untreated diabetic control group showed protective effect in diabetic rats. Pancreas sections in these groups showed that the pancreatic tissue retained to almost normal architecture.

Table-1: Effect of *Holostemma annularis* extracts on Blood glucose (mg/dL) in streptozotocin (STZ) induced diabetic rats.

Treatment and Dose	Serum Glucose (mg/dL)					
	Day's					
	0	4 th	7 th	10 th	13 th	16 th
Normal	85± 2.0	85± 2.0	85± 2.6	85±2.9	87±2.3	85±1.7
Diabetic Control	85± 1.7	194±5.2***	254± 8.8***	370±22***	346±22***	359±24***
Glibenclamide (5 mg/kg)	87± 2.3	200± 6.9	182±7.8***	171±8.7***	146±7.6***	116±4.6***
CEHA (150mg/kg)	85± 1.7	219± 9.9	182±4.5***	155±10***	132±9.8***	110±11***
CEHA (300 mg/kg)	85± 2.0	181± 7.6	164±6.9***	149±7.6***	141±7.6***	128±5.8***
AEHA (150 mg/kg)	85±2.6	191± 4.8	167±5.2***	140±3.7***	113±2.8***	97±3.8***
AEHA(300 mg/kg)	85±2.0	207± 14	194±21*	156±13***	133±11***	111±6.7***

Table-2: Effect of *Holostemma annularis* extracts on serum insulin (µu/ml) in STZ-induced diabetic rats.

Groups	Serum Insulin (µIU/ml)
Normal	11.8±1.8
Diabetic Control	8.7±1.9
Glibenclamide (5mg/kg)	10.4±1.6***
CEHA (150 mg/kg)	9.0±1.8
CEHA (300 mg/kg)	9.90±1.4
AEHA(150 mg/kg)	10.9±1.7*
AEHA (300 mg/kg)	11.00±1.9**

Table-3: Effect of *Holostemma annularis* extracts on urine creatinine & total proteins (mg/dL) in streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic rats.

Treatment and dose	Urine	
	Creatinine (mg/dL)	Total proteins (mg/dL)
Normal Control	0.32 ± 0.044	4.6 ± 0.004
Diabetic Control	0.19 ± 0.0045*	4.9 ± 0.17
Glibenclamide (5mg/kg)	0.21 ± 0.038	2.6 ± 0.18***
CEHA (150 mg/kg)	0.26 ± 0.030*	4.9 ± 0.37
CEHA (300 mg/kg)	0.60 ± 0.035***	7.2 ± 0.14***
AEHA (150 mg/kg)	0.31 ± 0.036**	1.5 ± 0.28***
AEHA (300 mg/kg)	0.28 ± 0.037*	1.6 ± 0.24***

A. Normal non-diabetic rat pancreas

E. CEHA (300 mg/kg) rat pancreas

F. AEHA (150 mg/kg) rat pancreas.

G. AEHA (300 mg/kg) rat pancreas.

Fig 1: Histopathology of Pancreas:

(A) Normal. Pancreas, showing no pathological changes. The exocrine pancreatic tissue composed of acini with draining ductless; the endocrine component is found as a nodule within the substance. (B) Pancreas (Diabetic Control) showing diffused necrotic changes of moderate to marked degree as a result of which they were significantly reduced in size and number. C Pancreas (Glibenclamide 5 mg/kg), after 14 days: showing improvement and minimal degenerative changes. (D &E) Pancreas (CEHA 150 &300 mg/kg, p.o.), after 14 days: showing less improvement or restoration of normal cellular population size of islets. (F&G) Pancreas (AEHA 150 & 300 mg/kg), after 14 days: showing marked improvement with nearly normal islets of Langerhans.

DISCUSSION:

Diabetes mellitus is a global disease that is a major cause of morbidity in the world [22]. This disorder is basically characterized by high levels of blood glucose caused by defective insulin production and action that are often responsible for severe health problems and the streptozotocin-induced diabetic rat is one of the animal models of human diabetes mellitus. Diabetes arises from irreversible destruction of pancreatic β cells, causing de-granulation and reduction of insulin secretion [23] and early death [24]. Much of the morbidity and mortality associated with diabetes is primarily attributed to micro vascular and macro vascular changes, such as atherosclerosis, retinopathy, nephropathy, coronary artery disease, cerebral vascular disease, and peripheral artery disease [25]. One of the reasons for injury related to hyperglycemia is the formation of glycated proteins, glucose oxidation, and increased free fatty acids [26].

In chloroform and alcohol extract of *Holostemma annularis* treated diabetic rats, the significant elevation of blood insulin may be due to the stimulation of insulin secretion from the existing β cells of pancreas. According to the present data glibenclamide reduces blood glucose levels in diabetes that is consistent with previous studies [27, 28]. Glibenclamide, one of the most widely used oral hypoglycemic agents in the treatment of diabetes mellitus, exerted its beneficial effects on extracellular site by opening Ca^{2+} channels to stimulate insulin secretion and also duodenal insulin releasing agent [29].

In streptozotocin group creatinine clearance was significantly lower relative to the normal control group indicating severe effect due to diabetes, similar to earlier reports [30]. *Holostemma annularis* chloroform and alcoholic extract treatment significantly improve renal creatinine clearance whereas glibenclamide failed to produce significant effect on STZ induced renal dysfunction. The similar activity of the chloroform and alcohol extract of *Holostemma annularis* may indicate that these extracts also act by stimulation of the islet cells of pancreas and insulin like effects on peripheral tissues. Glibenclamide is known to produce its effects by the stimulation of insulin release [31]. It is also known that glibenclamide is effective in moderate diabetic rats not in severe diabetic animals [32].

Intra-peritoneal administration of STZ selectively destroys the pancreatic insulin secreting β - cells living less number of active cells and resulting in type-1 diabetic state [33]. Similar results were obtained in the present study by both histopathological examinations and by serum glucose estimation.

IDDM is characterized by the infiltration of lymphocytes in to the pancreatic islets followed by the destruction of β - cells which leads to overt diabetes [34]. It has also been reported that rat pancreas with STZ induced diabetes; islet cells are shrunken with lytic and vascular changes [35]. Histopathological examination in the present in study are demonstrated all these histological changes in STZ diabetic control group. *Holostemma annularis* chloroform extract treatment prominently inhibited effect of STZ on β - cells of islets of langerhans in rat pancreas and was observed to be enlarged and free from lymphocytic infiltration. This result support and substantiates anti-hyperglycemic effects as evidenced in bio-chemical profile.

Holostemma annularis has been acclaimed as an important medicinal plant of Indian system of medicine and reported to be used in ophthalmia [36]. In folk medicine the roots rubbed to a paste and given in cold milk for the treatment of diabetes [37]. As per the mechanism of action concerned, we can propose that the anti-hyperglycemic activity of extracts may be due to potentiating the pancreatic secretions by pancreatic β -cells enlargement, inflammatory cell infiltration, anti-oxidant, cytoprotection and by increasing the glucose uptake. Thus the folk use of this plant has been validated by the study.

In our study, the antihyperglycemic effect of the roots of HA prevents STZ induced diabetes in rat's complications like the increases in serum glucose, urine creatinine and total proteins in urine. Administration of HA has been shown to prevent and improve insulin sensitivity. The chemical investigation of roots of HA revealed the presence of β -sitosterol, lupeol, α -amyrin and amino acids [38]. Many studies have validated the role of β -sitosterol and lupeol in the management of diabetes and hypercholesterolemia [39].

CONCLUSION:

The findings of the present study were effective in decreasing blood glucose level in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. All these models show that, it has long-term anti-diabetic activity without hypoglycemic side effects. The antihyperglycemic effects observed with methanol and alcohol extracts of *Holostemma annularis* prominent than glibenclamide demonstrating it as potent and safe anti-diabetic component then compared to glibenclamide even in crude form. Histopathological study, showing improvement with nearly normal islets of Langerhans, is showing marked improvement with normal architecture not only its efficacy in overcoming from diabetes but also autoimmune disorders.

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Competing Interests

We certify that we have participated sufficiently in the intellectual content, conception and design of this work or the analysis and interpretation of the data, as well as the writing of the manuscript entitled 'Antihyperglycemic activity of *Holostemma annularis* k. Schum root extracts in streptozotocin-induced diabetic *Wistar* rats', to take public responsibility for it and have agreed to have our name listed as a contributor. We believe the manuscript represents valid work. Neither this manuscript nor one with substantially similar content under our authorship has been published or is being considered for publication elsewhere.

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